

STUDYING ORGANIZATIONAL AND MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF LEADERS IN A FAMILY POLYCLINIC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7075891>

Abstract. Nowadays development of activities of medical institutions is considered to be important. Any organization in the field of medical services have to deal with management problems. In this article general methodological approaches to their activities are considered.

Keywords: management skills, family polyclinic, health care, medical services.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ РУКОВОДИТЕЛЕЙ СЕМЕЙНОЙ ПОЛИКЛИНИКИ

Аннотация. В настоящее время важным считается развитие деятельности медицинских учреждений. Любая организация в сфере медицинских услуг сталкивается с проблемами управления. В статье рассматриваются общие методологические подходы к их деятельности.

Ключевые слова: управленческие навыки, семейная поликлиника, здравоохранение, медицинские услуги.

INTRODUCTION

The organization of the activities of medical institutions is of particular importance at the present stage of development of health care. Management problems are reflected in all the concepts and programs for reform of the health care system in the country proposed for discussion. Therefore, it seems relevant to consider the general methodological approaches to the activities of organizations involved in the provision of medical services to the population. The experience of foreign countries shows that in the management of medical institutions, new trends are now becoming more and more distinct, which are of undoubted both practical and theoretical interest. All organizations, no matter what area they operate in, face common management challenges. Based on general patterns, specific management methods are built depending on the conditions under which they are applied. Health care is no exception. The specificity of primary management is due, first of all, to the fact that health care is a special field of activity that differs significantly from other types of activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of the study. Conduct an analysis of the activities of the heads of services of medical institutions in the field of studying the factors affecting the organization and management of primary care institutions.

Research methodology.

- studied literary sources on the topic
- Sanitary-statistical analyzes were carried out
- conducted sociological surveys.

RESULTS

Women leaders are now represented in all fields of activity. There are many examples of how superbly female leaders do their job. Moreover, there are areas of production where only a female leader has a chance of success, because the management of a women's team has its own difficult specifics. Based on the conducted research, we can talk about what distinguishes a

female leader from a male leader: high insight, cunning, imaginative perception of the world, daydreaming, strong self-control of behavior, emotional instability, anxiety. The effectiveness of managerial activity depends on the abilities of the leader. Of the personal qualities of leaders, we noted such as - high efficiency. In the modern world, this quality is especially appreciated by the leaders of organizations, as they are aimed at obtaining the maximum effect, and the efficiency of employees is a necessary tool for obtaining it.

- education - all managers have higher education: medical.

- communication skills. Ability to establish good relations with subordinates, heads of other departments, higher management.

- self-management, self-criticism. A person who does not know how to look at himself from the outside, soberly assess his actions, cannot competently manage the team.

- delicacy, tact in working with subordinates, it is possible to build relationships with subordinates in such a way that they enjoy authority over them.

- purposefulness. For a modern leader, it is very important to set the right goal and go to it in the shortest possible way.

DISCUSSION

According to the results, it was noted that all managers have developed professional competencies, such as purposefulness, high efficiency, sociability and tact, restraint and self-criticism are little expressed, as well as the business qualities of managers. According to the results, some business qualities of the leader were rated with low scores (2-6 points):

- The manager successfully copes with non-routine tasks (47.1%)

- The manager successfully resolves conflict situations within the unit (52.9%)

- The manager shows loyalty to the organization (64.7%)

- The leader shows the required level of initiative: (58.8%)

- The manager has the necessary professional knowledge, skills and abilities to successfully manage the unit (35.2%)

- The manager successfully motivates employees (64.7%).

Sufficient provision of organizations with the necessary labor resources, their rational use, a high level of labor productivity are of great importance for improving the efficiency of activities. The staff of the organization is one of the main resources of the organization. The author assessed the completeness of the use of labor resources by the number of days and hours worked by one employee for the analyzed period, as well as by the degree of use of the working time fund. The data show that the available labor resources are used insufficiently, on average, one worker worked 257 days instead of 276, and therefore, the whole-day loss of working time amounted to 19 days per worker, i.e. 9633 hours. To study the leadership style, the author conducted testing and revealed that the leaders of the seed polyclinic use an authoritarian management style aimed at a high degree of task orientation. Also, after analyzing the sociometric study, the author concluded that the socio-psychological climate in the company's team is rather tense, since in percentage terms they were: 31% - "outcasts"; 14% - "white crows"; 3% - "isolated"; 9% - "leaders"; 43% - "accepted".

CONCLUSIONS

Sufficient provision of enterprises with the necessary labor resources, their rational use, are of great importance for improving the efficiency of activities. In the activities of medical institutions, the management style is mainly authoritarian. To achieve the most effective

leadership style, the leader should cooperate with subordinates, draw their attention to the formation of the task and decision-making, not exercise strict control over them, sometimes switching to a liberal democratic style. The most important factor influencing efficiency is the socio-psychological climate, dissatisfaction with the work of employees. The most important factor influencing efficiency is the socio-psychological climate, dissatisfaction with the work of employees. The team cannot be called very close-knit, and the socio-psychological climate is “healthy”, comfortable.

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